

The Impact of Organizational Justice, Job Stress, Coworker Competence, and Coworker Warmth on Turnover Intention: A Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Private Education Sector of Karachi

Umaima Riaz¹, Mariam Shahid², Saima Akhtar³, Aashi Arman⁴

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of organizational justice, job stress, coworker competence, and coworker warmth on turnover intention: a mediating role of job satisfaction in the private education sector of Karachi. In this study, a quantitative methodology was applied, and a total sample size of 300 respondents was obtained from various universities throughout Karachi, Pakistan, through an online, self-administered survey out of which 267 responses were received. The research evaluates previous studies on the effects of job stress, organizational justice, colleague competence, and coworker warmth on intention to leave the company. Five hypotheses are generated in this study to examine the correlation between these factors. The findings show that the intention to leave the company is significantly influenced by organizational justice, job stress, coworker competence, and coworker warmth. For this purpose, the data was collected and thump rule it in SPSS version 21.0, SMART PLS, 3.0. The data was analyzed through PLS for the structural equation modeling (SEM) measurement of both reflective and formative constructs. On the basis of this research future recommendation are added.

Keywords: organizational justice, job stress, coworker competence, coworker warmth, turnover intention, job satisfaction

1. Background to the study

In today's era unnecessary weakening and high turnover intension is neither in light of a valid concern for manager nor is it useful for employment movement of an employee. Turnover intension is basically related to organizational justice who implies the honesty and appraisal of treatment got by an individual in the organization (Cropanzano & Greenberg, 1997). Employee turnover is a complicated issue for organizations in Karachi Pakistan (Reina et al., 2018). In addition, lack of professional development opportunities or limited opportunities for career advancement can also contribute to high turnover intention in the education sector. Teachers and other education professionals may feel like they are not able to grow in their careers, leading them to seek employment elsewhere. Overall, addressing turnover intention in the education sector requires a multifaceted approach that includes addressing issues of job satisfaction, burnout, and professional development opportunities (Dharmawan et al., 2015).

Education assumes an import function in the advancement and improvement of a state. Progress of any nation relies on its education rate and nature of schooling in that nation. Consequently, it is the critical needs of countries (Amir, Sharf & Khan, 2020). The education area of Karachi Pakistan are expressly challenging issue of turnover, on the grounds that there is big measure of tension on degree granting establishments to make graduates, so awful necessities of corporate area can be pleased (Ashraf, Ahmad & Haider, 2016 Wilson & Chatman 2020). Researchers spend maximum time to satisfy their employee in the education sector (Durrani, 2019). The most usually survey antecedents to turnover recognized in writing are job satisfaction, intension to leave, organizational duty, employment behavior conduct, and monetary variables (Chishti, 2019). Employee turnover intention in the education sector can have significant implications on the quality of education and student outcomes. When teachers or other education professionals have high turnover intentions, it can result in instability in the school or institution, difficulty in maintaining continuity of curriculum and teaching practices, and a negative impact on student learning. (Hanif & Pervz, 2004). Concerns about organizational justice are imitated from a couple of particular sides of employee sought after life. The term justice notice to the level to which representatives see works environment procedures, collaborations and results to be simple in nature (Karatepe & Olugbade, 2017; Sattar et al., 2017). Job stress is one of the principle working environment prosperity risks for representatives in created and non-industrial countries (Paul, 2002; Danna & Griffin, 2002). The most inspected negative workplace supervisor lead is harming the board, considering the way that in spite of the way that it is a low base-rate thing, there is evidence that its results are critical (Zellars, Tepper, & Duffy, 2002). Coworker competence as a key contributing part for how employees see their coworkers, which prompts increasing individual and organizational outcomes (Davidson et al., 2011). Singular practices and judgment may also be driven by specialist examinations of colleague warmth. This relies upon the game plan that individuals need to criticize others subject to warmth and competence (Cuddy, Glick, & Beninger, 2011; Karatepe & Olugbade, 2017; Li et al., 2017). Job satisfaction suggest to representatives' views and their level of satisfaction an individual gets for his/her services regardless of whether they are negative and positive. This investigation could support managers and instructors to follow the advancing view of personnel job satisfaction, turnover intension and improve the business related variables that can prompt more dedicated, fulfilled and enabled employees (Chishti, 2019).

¹ Lecturer, Indus University, Karachi, Pakistan, umaima.riaz@indus.edu.pk

² Lecturer Indus University, Karachi, Pakistan, mariam.shahid@indus.edu.pk

³ Assistant Professor, DPA, UOK, Pakistan, Saima.akhtar@uok.edu.pk

⁴ PhD Research Scholar, DPA, UOK, Pakistan, armani_1980@yahoo.com

1.1. Statement of the Problem

In today's era, switching jobs for a better working environment is no longer frowned upon since employees especially in bank of Pakistan have a great opportunity for a better prospective (Azeem et al., 2017). Now it is not so easy to retain employees with the growing market opportunities because employees demand for better working conditions. Due to employees leaving, banks not only suffer from the loss of an employee with knowledge of their organization but also, lose valuable the relationship built with the customers that were associated with a particular employee (Abate, Schaefer & Pavone, 2018). Turnover consistently stayed a significant issue for organizations particularly in education area with representative deficiencies. The dual responsibilities of work and family lives are upsetting their work-life balance (Ajaz, Mehmood & Kashif, 2015). The turnover issue is filling quickly in Karachi's education area (Husain et al., 2015). Worker's turnover is a worldwide fact in the current period; practically all organizations challenge the issue of turnover intensification (Dess & Shaw, 2001). Especially in the education sector there is increasing turnover ratios, which leave organizations to bear heavy costs of recruitment, selection and training in Pakistan (Pahi et al., 2016; Ahmad et al., 2016; Fayaz et al., 2019). According to Azeem & Humayon, (2017) high rate of turnover in Pakistan is due to abusive supervisors and lack of substantial working conditions. Every year, hundreds of employees quit their position, which leave organization in the critical position of rehiring employees while having their productivity at stake. This not only adds to the recruitment, selection and training costs but also takes up time and other resources that could be utilized towards the profitability of the organization (Pahi et al., 2016; Ahmad et al., 2016; Fayaz et al., 2016). Coworker competence can be utilized to arrive at the objectives and to perform effectively. Many analysts have disclosed those workers who need directors to comprehend their necessities, give them needed help and treat them based on value and justice (Albino, 2018). Coworker warmth is completely influenced by the conduct of the organization (Susskind, Kacmar, & Borchgrevink, 2003). When there is warmth in the representative's conduct to one another, workers will in general build up some holding which prompts the reducing of lower turnover goals in the education sector (Manning, Davidson, & Manning, 2005).

The purpose behind this quantitative investigation is to notice the turnover expectation approaches of standards in their initial five years in this situation at secretly held instruction area of Karachi.

1.2. Research Question

What is the impact of organizational justice, job stress, coworker competence, and coworker warmth on turnover intention: a mediating role of job satisfaction in the private education sector of Karachi?

1.3. Social Exchange Theory

The social exchange theory (Kerlinger, 1979) proffers concrete theoretical background for the assumptions of this study a theory is a set of interrelated constructs or variables, definitions and propositions that presents a systematic view of a phenomenon by specifying relations among variables, with the purpose of explaining a natural phenomenon. The social exchange theoretical point of view is to advocate for a shared balance of obligation between the two gatherings. For example, among the employees-employers relationship, it is observable that employees sacrifice their information, skills, and capacities for rewards. These rewards can be multifaceted; it can be notified of money and so on or rather something insubstantial like regard, pride, personality, and equality. Constantly, the psychologist said that fairness is a fundamental factor for each employee to be fulfilled with their job. Consequently, it can be derived from the theoretical points of view clarified over those employees that are treated without discrimination are expected to have a positive and high level of fulfillment and when there is fulfillment, there will be an inspiration to keep on working with their organization.

1.4. Organizational justice and Job Satisfaction

The major approach of organizational justice is equity theory proposes that individuals are motivated to maintain fair or equitable relationships among themselves and to avoid those relationships that are unfair or inequitable (Ghran, 2019). Human resource management departments aim to set up guidelines and directions in order to sustain organizational justice surrounded by organization. Organizational justice has become a wide spread concern for many researchers. Organizational behavior and Organizational Theory realm suggested organizational justice as a crucial concept and organizational practice in modern organizational management (Chen et al., 2015). Improve organizational justice may have a direct and positive effect on the performance and sustainability of any organization (Dundar & Tabanali, 2012; Silva & Caetano, 2014) In past, number of research studies has supported a positive relationship between higher level of organizational justice and job satisfaction (Karkoulian et al., 2016).

Hypothesis 1: Organizational justice has a significant impact on job satisfaction

1.5. Job Stress and Job satisfaction

The relationship between job stress and job satisfaction the employer has been examined by many researchers. Job satisfaction may protect workers from stressors (Hoboubi, 2017). Current data in the literature indicates that the perception of a stressful work environment favors employee decisions to truly leave their organization (Ismail, 2015). Job stress is the consequence of inequality between one's hopes and real situations at work. Job stress is due to organizational aspects, long work hours, lack of organizational support and organizational change, lack of support from supervisors and colleagues, and conflict with demands and pressures. Stress leads to aggression and low job satisfaction when it functions as a negative factor. Satisfaction

is a regulating factor for stress. High levels of work stress are associated with low levels of job satisfaction. Job stressors are predictive for job dissatisfaction and a greater propensity to leave the organization. High levels of work stress are associated with low levels of job satisfaction. Job stressors are predictive for job dissatisfaction and a greater propensity to leave the organization (Hoboubi, 2016).

Hypothesis 2: Job stress has a significant impact on job satisfaction

1.6. Coworker competence and Job satisfaction

Coworker competence is vital for the organization's success (Haque & Aston, 2016). Past studies have found that a positive organizational culture provides job satisfaction to employees and harnesses a long-term relationship with the organization (Chong et al., 2018). Coworker competence refers to a set of behaviors, ethics, values, sense of comradeship, mutual support etc. High levels of competence elicit favorable outcomes (Cuddy, Fiske, & Glick, 2007). Coworker competence is a psychological state that characterizes worker relations with work (Dan Metiboba, 2012). A person will have better work results if based on better work commitments; this is stated in research (Harinoto & Bogetriatmanto, 2018). The results of a study of a number of studies found that work competence influences job satisfaction (Lotunani et al., 2014; Setyaningtyas et al., 2013).

Hypothesis 3: Coworker competence has a significant impact on job satisfaction

1.7. Coworker warmth and Job satisfaction

Coworker warmth is involved with cooperation between the individuals and is linked with the services which are helpful to others (Brambilla, Hewstone, & Colucci, 2013). There are studies that have argued that employees warm ability influence employees turnover of intention through job satisfaction and organizational commitment, noting that the two attitudes of work is believed to significantly reduce the intentions of turnover (Kang 2014; Karatepe, 2009). Job satisfaction explains employee's expectations in the relevant parameters to the satisfaction (Owner & Ghaffor, 2012). According to John the client's mind is a complex set of ideas that no human is fully predictable.

Hypothesis 4: Coworker warmth has a significant impact on job satisfaction

1.8. Job satisfaction and turnover intention

The other topic that has extensively been examined in the employee turnover intention research is job satisfaction. Truly speaking, job satisfaction demonstrates the number of satisfied individuals with their jobs. In general, job satisfaction was found to be negatively related to turnover (Griffeth et al, 2000; Khatri et al, 2001; Tett & Meyer, 1993; Vong, 2003). In efficient compensation programs worker should intend to raise the stage of satisfaction with motivation and reward workers for their share to the improvement of productivity. Most of the studies concluded that employee satisfaction is the most forecasting aspect in turnover. Griffeth et al (2000) defined remuneration association with supervisor, working conditions and job content as different cause in employees' satisfaction.

Hypothesis 5: Job satisfaction has a significant impact on turnover intension

2. Hypothesized model of the current study

Figure-1

3. Review of the Related Studies

The turnover of employees should understand and make it specific that surroundings provide a respectable fair amount in a distribution of rewards and fairness in actions guiding decision-making process. The absence of organizational justice would lead to turnover intention. According to this study, there is a significant relationship between organizational and turnover intention. Questionnaires were sent to 340 education sector employees and completed 600 were received and performed regression techniques were analysed for the result. There are few limitations of this study. The very first limitation is its reliance on the self-detailing questionnaires for estimating the factors of the study. Second, the current study only analyzed turnover intentions of employees (Arif, 2018).

Coworker competency refers to a set of behaviors, ethics, values, sense of comradeship, mutual support and so on, which play a significant role in keeping the employees happy and committed (Khan & Qadir, 2016). The results reveal that coworker competence has a positive influence on work engagement in the education sector. Approximately 600 questionnaires were circulated among employees of education sectors using a simple random sampling technique. In this conclusion, job satisfaction has a basic issue to business privileged, guidelines makers, HR directors, supervisors, organizational advisors, and organizations everywhere (Arfat et al., 2017).

Fundamentally, this present study's outcomes confirm that coworker warmth can be of an incentive in enhancing job satisfaction, which will consequently prompt to the reduction of turnover intention. Instead of; job satisfaction mediates the relationship between coworker warmth and turnover intentions. In this paper, the PLS-SEM technique is used and the sample data is 82 employees were received. The importance of warmth as a crucial determinant of job satisfaction and turnover intention. Limitations have been discovered with respect to this study. The limitation is connected with the common technique variance (Al-Shbiel et al., 2018).

4. Methodology

The research has useful relationship research design by its reason is a quantitative research method which is utilized to evaluate the connection between dependent and independent variables and also mediator variable. In this research, quantitative research is utilized which is particular and deductive in nature, comprises of structure close-ended questions and dependent on numerical analysis that gives results in statically structure or affirm the variables with their results. Estimations which define the agreement and common views of the linked to the content. The explanatory study is directed to discover the issue which was not considered in depth, or explanatory research isn't utilized to give some conclusive outcome however it helps to know the issued all the more proficiently. This research depends on a correlation study examined the value of variables that are related to the issue (Ary et al., 2018). The target population is characterized geographical limits and components. To examine the worker's turnover intention which is the dependent variable for this information was collected from the education sector which was target viewers from those administrative level and entry level and there is no gender discrimination (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). A convenience sampling method is that the most part used to aim the population that is simply available. Likelihood sampling is used in this research. There is no sexual difference education sector employees participate in this research. Primary data were utilized as a technique or process to gather the data and it is self-managed for the researcher. Close-ended questionnaire was used to gather the data. All the variables were scaling question to calculate the responses of the member or respondents like Likert scale were utilized to evaluate. In this study researcher has used smart PLS, modeling (measurement model), structural model, hypothesis testing, and mediation analysis and cross-validity redundancy analysis using blinding techniques to find out the impact dependent variable (turnover intention) on more than two independent variables (organizational justice, job stress, coworker competence, coworker warmth) and a mediating role of (job satisfaction) with the procedure of questionnaire.

5. Data analysis

5.1. Hypothesis testing using SEM

Scholar tested the approximation model to confirm the validity and reliability of the variables. Also, there is essential to draw the model on smart PLS and run a PLS algorithm to examine the convergent validity. In the time, the average variance extracted (AVE) that should be more than 0.5 which is measured an acceptable and internal reliability for instance composite reliability (CR) should be more than 0.7 that measured as agreeable. But the values are less than the range value, or decrease the scale like 0.4 to 0.7 if it falls in the fit range; at that point it is good usually the items which are under the range must be removed. After this technique at this time checks the discriminant validity that reveals all the values of the column which is shown in table that must be greater and equal to the square root of the AVE. Besides, a scholar likewise studies the R square value that presents the level of predicting endogenous and exogenous variables that are more than 0.1.

5.2. Measurement model (Outer Model)

This model reveals the reflective model which displays that arrowhead from the variables sharp towards the Likert scale item. the reliability analysis, there is obligatory to survey the outer loading which appears as in the table: that describe all the items are full on their separate factor and their value must be greater than 0.7 (Yoo & Alavi, 2001). It is advised that each pointer should be scaled at least 0.70 then it and in count considered as the thumb rule, therefore (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Mena,

2012) reveal that value from 0.5 to 0.7 likewise included or acknowledge as a valid value. In the interim, the value 0.4 or below for this range are rejected from the factor to follow every one of these series in this model testing the outer loading. As per is falling in the wrong value nearby each value is above than 0.5 which is acceptable. This model verified that the items which have under 0.5 or patent as red in Ave column are excluded from the model remove items from variables.

Figure-2

5.3. Convergent Validity

To check the approximation model, there is vital to check the convergent validity to determine the connection between two variables and convergent validity defines how positively variables are linked with separately other (Cunningham, Preacher & Banji, 2001).

This table 1 shows the outer loading, composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) which determines that all values above than 0.5 that mean average variance extracted is precise and composite reliability values also above than 0.7 it validates the reliability of the variables and statistical position.

5.4. Discriminant Validity

It determines the positive and negative effect on the concept and various construct in the model are connected with every constructor. They haven't any connection to know the discriminant validity there is predictable to see the value of Fornell-Larcker criteria (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) to construct the level of consequences (Hair et al., 2012) value must be greater than and size that validates the square of the relationship of the variance. All the sloping values are the square root of average variance extracted (AVEs) and underestimates is the correlation of changed variables which is less than the overhead values.

The values of Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) should to be less than 0.85 which orders the fear of discriminant validity. The Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT), it's a new code for tentative discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table-1

	Outer Loadings	CR	(AVE)
CC1	0.811	0.870	0.573
CC2	0.775		
CC3	0.761		
CC4	0.725		
CC5	0.709		
CW4	0.840	0.854	0.664
CW5	0.709		
CW6	0.885		
JS1	0.883	0.955	0.809
JS2	0.914		
JS3	0.939		
JS4	0.845		
JS5	0.913		
OJ1	0.783	0.906	0.615
OJ2	0.799		
OJ3	0.776		
OJ4	0.833		
OJ5	0.773		
OJ7	0.739		
TI2	0.827	0.822	0.607
TI4	0.780		
TI6	0.727		
WS2	0.872	0.856	0.667
WS4	0.722		
WS5	0.848		

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker

	CC	CW	JS	OJ	TI	WS
coworker competence	0.757					
coworker warmth	0.132	0.815				
job satisfaction	0.572	0.138	0.900			
organizational justice	0.488	0.269	0.522	0.784		
turnover intention	-0.105	0.012	-0.245	-0.184	0.779	
work stress	-0.144	0.018	-0.116	-0.053	0.025	0.816

Table 3: Heterotrait –Monotrait Ratio

	CC	CW	JS	OJ	TI	WS
coworker competence						
coworker warmth	0.164					
job satisfaction	0.649	0.155				
organizational justice	0.578	0.337	0.568			
turnover intention	0.134	0.082	0.295	0.223		
work stress	0.181	0.054	0.133	0.087	0.097	

5.5. Bootstrapping

Bootstrapping similarly functional at 5000 at range value. This table expression an assembly model. This table proves the relationship between variables to variables and mediator

Table 4: Adjusted-R

R Square Adjusted	
job satisfaction	0.397
turnover intention	0.056

This table defines the weak relationship in the model. For example, it symbolizes as the weak relation between variables there is no fit result in this model. (Wetzels, Odekerken-Schröder, & Van Oppen, 2009).

5.6. Assessment of Q-square

Blindfolding is the other method to determine the authenticity of variables (Hair et al., 2012) and this process obtain by cross-validation severance to control the analytical position of the present model (Geisser, 1975) industrialized the Q² test that validates the practical values and its limitations

Table 5: Blindfolding Q-square

Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	
job satisfaction	0.319
turnover intention	0.030

This table determines the valuations of analytical significance that requirement be > 0 (above .0) for existence dependent variables. There are two types of Q-square initial one is identified as cross-validated commonality and second, identified as redundancy (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The model shows job satisfaction is 0.319 which exemplifies that it's significant impact on the exogenous whereas, TI 0.030 that explain it significant impact on other variables.

Figure-3

In this table 6 shows the path coefficient and the result of significant and insignificant both the result shown in this table. As the complete shows the original sample value and the P-value of the exogenous and endogenous elements. Path analysis shows the relationship of dependent and independent variables. It has been finished by performing bootstrapping. In the event that the P-value is under 0.05, at that point the outcome is significant (Hair Jr et al., 2016). In this table shows the path

coefficient and the result of significant and insignificant both the result shown in this table. As the complete shows the original sample value and the P-value of the exogenous and endogenous elements. Path analysis shows the relationship of dependent and independent variables. It has been finished by performing bootstrapping. In the event that the P-value is under 0.05, at that point the outcome is significant (Hair Jr et al., 2016).

Table 6: Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation	T ((O/STDEV))	Statistics	P Values	Remarks
coworker competence -> job satisfaction	0.411	0.066		6.237	0.000	Accepted
coworker warmth -> job satisfaction	-0.002	0.044		0.038	0.969	Not Accepted
job satisfaction -> turnover intention	-0.245	0.046		5.366	0.000	Accepted
organizational justice -> job satisfaction	0.320	0.058		5.541	0.000	Accepted
work stress -> job satisfaction	-0.040	0.056		0.716	0.474	Not Accepted

6. Discussion

This chapter portrays the data investigation with detail explanation which defines by the assistance of figures, table and model diagrams. The initial step is to process data analysis, the researcher collects the pilot study (n=50) the purpose of the pilot gathering was to check the reliability and correlation of the variables that utilized in this study. Subsequently, the dataset must be clean by an alternate procedure which is called as a data screening process includes the missing values, out of range values, univariate and multivariate outliers. This procedure was an important step to continue with the further analysis. Once a dataset cleaned from the mistake at this time it's prepared to move for the major test that is smart PLS. For this, it's essential that data file ought to be saved on (*.csv) from which it easily imports to smart PLS file. The initial step is to decide the composite reliability (CR) and Average variance extracted (AVE) which must be according to a criterion value for instance CR must be greater than 0.7 and AVE ought to be greater than 0.5 this value portrays the convergent validity. Where to discover the discriminant validity there is expected to check the Fornell & Larcker which is the square root of AVE value and the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) that characterizes there are no sub-dimensions values. The blindfolding clarifies the Q-square and bootstrapping shows the R-square that is too mention in the outcome interpretation. These results are additionally processed to recognize the mediation, which was portrayed by the mediation analysis on which direct and and their detailed explanation helps the person who reads to identify with their analysis and relationship of variables The section encloses the hypothesis summary that gives the entire image of the supported and not supported the variables.

7. Conclusion

The main purpose of this study is to examine the relationship among dependent variable as well as independent variables along with mediator. A sample of 300 was collected in which only 267 data was usable to check the impact of variables. Job satisfaction is thought to impact their work outcomes, for example, organizational commitment and turnover intentions. The adequacy of selection, training, and supervisory programs ought to be measured to some degree by their impact on employee's satisfaction with their work. Managers should attempt to increment of job satisfaction of employees. It is clear that high job satisfaction and organizational commitment will maintain a strategic distance from turnover aim and genuine turnover. Each employee has various types of requirements and expectations and it is difficult to fulfill each need and expectation of the employees. Both employee and boss should attempt to create a working condition that they will work in a happy, motivated and productive atmosphere to arrive at the certain goals Employees in an association have consistently been a key asset, as their takeoffs could significantly affect the execution of the association's strategies and may ultimately cause an equal decrease in productivity. All things considered, employee retention was critical to the drawn out development and achievement of the organization. Holding the best employees would guarantee fulfillment and viable succession planning (Mello, 2006). It would likewise improve speculator's certainty, as they were worried about the association's ability to act in such manners that would decidedly impact the estimation of their investment in the organization. Subsequently, there was no doubt that uncontrolled employee turnover could harmed the dependability of the organization and thusly the public economy.

7.1. Recommendation

Following are the suggestions based on the outcomes and conclusion of the current study to the private banking sector of Karachi. It's difficult to change what you're not estimating. It's essential to gather the information cautiously, understanding that all turnovers aren't equivalent and that how you measure representative turnover has any kind of effect. Justice happens when employees accept that results are equitable. These results are either unmistakable, such as pay, or intangible, such as positive feedback. At the point when employees accept that they are being paid or treated similarly, at that point these

outcomes in justice. Job satisfactions of employees who consider their manager and co-workers warm and competent are altogether higher than the individuals who assess them as cold and incompetent. Likewise, employees who feel that they work with a warm and competent manager and co-workers will in general create lower turnover expectations.

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